

Evaluation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program in Poverty Alleviation in Enrekang Regency

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Abstract:- The purpose of this research is to find out and analyze the implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT) program in Enrekang Regency. This study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. This approach aims to provide an overview regarding the evaluation of the implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT) program in poverty alleviation in Enrekang Regency. The results of the study show that the implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT) program has not been effective in overcoming poverty in Enrekang District. This is due to the lack of the role of the local government Village in providing a clear understanding to the community regarding the method of submitting and determining Beneficiary Groups (KPM) so that the community becomes confused and lacks information regarding Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT) in Enrekang Regency.

Keywords:- Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT), Poverty, Beneficiary Groups (KPM).

I. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is a long-term problem faced by a country in an effort to increase real national income. Economic growth measures how much success a country has in producing goods and services that are influenced by factors that experience an increase in quantity and quality so as to improve people's welfare.

Fig 1 Trend of Economic Growth in Enrekang Regency for 2017-2020
X: Period

Y: Percentage of Economic Growth
Source: BPS Enrekang Regency, 2021

The Economic Growth of Enrekang Regency when compared with the Economic growth of South Sulawesi Province, it can be seen that from the 2017-2020 period there has always been a positive trend. Even in 2017 it was 6.84%. In 2018 it experienced a slowdown of 3.26% and in 2019 it experienced another increase of 5.43%. Then in 2020, it again experienced a slowdown of only 1.25%. This is caused by a decrease in the value of services obtained by each of the reduced factors of economic production. One of the reasons is the COVID-19 pandemic.

Poverty is an urgent national problem and requires steps to overcome and a systematic, integrated and comprehensive approach [1]. These efforts must be aimed at reducing the burden and fulfilling the basic rights of citizens properly to lead and develop a dignified life.

As the results of research conducted by [2], said that Indonesian people often adopt a culture by modifying their situation to become "poor", so they can receive social assistance programs under the pretext of participating in state funds. The habit of taking shortcuts to get the program so that the program is not optimal in its achievements.

Recognizing the importance of reducing poverty for the sustainability of the nation and state, the Government places efforts to reduce poverty as a top priority [3]. This is stated in the 2005-2025 National RPJP and is in line with the global agreement in realizing the achievement of the MDGs to reduce poverty by 50 percent by 2015 through the Millennium Declaration.

In general, the target for achieving poverty alleviation programs is to improve people's welfare and reduce the number of poor people. According to [4] Regarding the target achievement of the poverty alleviation program, the government formulates achievement targets based on existing development planning mechanisms.

The target for achieving the poverty alleviation program can be measured based on a time scale, namely short-term, medium-term and long-term targets at both the national and regional levels [5]. The short term target refers to the RKPD which is set every year. Meanwhile, the medium-term target refers to the 5 (five) yearly plan stipulated in the National RPJM, as well as the Regional RPJM. The long-term target

refers to the 25-year development plan stipulated in the National RPJP at the national scope and the Regional RPJP. The targets are in the form of numbers, namely; (1) Target of RPJPN (2004-2025) in 2025: Poverty rate <5%; (2) RPJMN Targets (2020-2024) in 2024: Poverty Rate 6.5-7%; (3) Enrekang Regency's RPJMD target (2018-2023 <10%) in 2023: Poverty rate of 10.37%.

The Poverty Rate and Number of Poor Population in Enrekang Regency in 2017-2020 experienced an average decreasing trend each year. In 2017 the number of poor people was 26,710 people or 13.16%, in 2018 the number of poor people was 25,530 people or around 12.49%, in 2019 the number of poor people was 25,400 people or around 12.33%, and in 2020 the number of poor people is 25,250 people or 12.17%. With this achievement, the indicator for reducing the poverty rate based on the final target of the RPJMD, namely the Poverty Level (<10%) has not been achieved or the achievement level is 84.24%. This needs to be a concern of the Regional Government in the framework of preparing the next period's RPJMD to boost programs/activities that can directly boost the reduction in regional poverty rates.

The reduction in the poverty rate from year to year is strongly influenced by national government programs that are pro-people, such as Free Education and Health, rice for the poor, improvement of slum housing at the public works agency, direct assistance to the community, house renovations, Agricultural Seed Assistance, Cattle assistance, Tuition Assistance for Students (South Sulawesi Provincial Program). Whereas for the district scale, namely assistance from regional apparatus to poor households, assistance with cattle and goat seeds, subsidies for rice for the poor. . In 2017 the local government has fully subsidized the distribution of Raskin rice from the Raskin distribution depot warehouse to distribution points.

Fig 2 Poverty Rate of Enrekang Regency Year 2017-2020
 X: Period
 Y: Percentage of Poverty Rate

For the number of poor people, it can be described that there has been a reduction in the number of poor people. In 2017 there were 26,710 people, in 2018 there were 25,530 people, in 2019 around 25,400 people. However, in 2020 there was a decrease in the poverty rate, although not significantly, namely to 25,250 thousand people. Even though the trend has

decreased in poverty, in the regional context when compared to other districts in South Sulawesi Province, the poverty rate in Enrekang Regency is still classified as an area with a moderate poverty rate (above 10%). Another cause is related to accurate data sources from existing data provider stakeholders. As a follow up, there is a need for a poverty data base which is a conclusion from the data source from the device.

Law Number 11 of 2009 concerning Social Welfare defines social welfare as a condition of fulfilling the material, spiritual and social needs of citizens so that they can live properly and be able to develop themselves, so that they can carry out their social functions. One of the basic material needs for humans is food.

Food is an element in the concept of social welfare Suradi in [6]. According to Law Number 18 of 2012 concerning Food, food is the most important basic need and affects the life of every human being.

To measure poverty, BPS uses the concept of ability to meet basic needs (basic needs approach). With this approach, poverty is seen as an economic inability to meet basic food and non-food needs as measured from the expenditure side. The method used is to calculate the Poverty Line (GK), which consists of two components, namely the Food Poverty Line (GKM) and the Non-Food Poverty Line (GKNM) (BPS Enrekang Regency, 2021).

The government has issued various policies in overcoming the poverty of people in Indonesia [7]. One of them is by providing assistance in the form of food. It aims to improve the standard of living of the people.

The government has provided Food/Rastra subsidies since 1997 in the form of Special Market Operations (OPK), among others, to respond to the economic crisis and prolonged drought. In 2002 the OPK program changed to the Raskin Subsidy (rice for the poor) by mandating the Ministry of Social Affairs (Kemensos) to receive an assignment as the Budget User Authority (KPA) for Food Subsidies/Raskin. Furthermore, in 2016 the term Raskin was changed to Rastra or Rice for Prosperous Families which was given to 15.6 million families. As directed by the President for social assistance to be distributed in a non-cash manner, in 2017 the Rastra transformation began from rice subsidies to social assistance in the form of Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT).

One of the programs established by the government to reduce the burden on society in meeting basic needs is the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT). The BPNT program is food assistance that is distributed non-cash from the government to Beneficiary Families (KPM) every month, through an electronic account mechanism that is used only to buy food at places that have collaborated with banks [8; 9]. The BPNT program is organized by the government in the context of increasing effectiveness and efficiency, targeting the

distribution of social assistance and encouraging inclusive finance.

To support the implementation of the BPNT program, the President of the Republic of Indonesia has enacted Presidential Decree Number 63 of 2017, concerning Distribution of Non-Cash Social Assistance. The President greatly appreciated the BPNT program because it was able to reduce the expenditure burden on KPM by fulfilling some of the food needs, providing balanced nutrition to KPM participants, increasing the targeting accuracy and timing of receiving food assistance and pushing towards sustainable development.

As the government has issued the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program in the context of overcoming poverty. To make the distribution of food aid more effective, in 2020 the General Guidelines for the Staple Food Program were issued and even revised (Change I) in the same year (Year 2020). The guideline discusses in detail related to the implementation or application of the distribution of assistance.

Based on the General Guidelines for the 2020 Change I Staple Food Program, the implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program in general includes the preparation stage, the KKS registration and distribution stage, the education and socialization stage, the distribution of aid funds, and the utilization of aid funds stage.

The General Guidelines for the 2020 Change I Staple Food Program are also regulated in relation to the criteria for beneficiaries of the basic food program, namely families with the lowest socioeconomic conditions in the implementation area according to the program ceiling provided by the Government, hereinafter referred to as the Beneficiary Families (KPM) of the Sembako program whose names are included in the List of Beneficiaries (DPM) of the Sembako program and determined by the KPA at the Ministry of Social Affairs.

The Regional Government of Enrekang Regency followed up on this policy by issuing Decree of the Regent of Enrekang Number 437/KEP/V/2021 concerning the Establishment of the 2021 Enrekang Regency Staple Food Program Coordination Team, sub-district, and village/kelurahan as well as the duties and functions of each position.

Table 1 Data of Beneficiaries of Non-Cash Program Assistance in Enrekang Regency for 2019 – 2021

No	Disctrict	Number of Recipients (Year)		
		2019 (Month 6-12)	2020	2021
1.	Alla	850	1547	1388
2.	Anggeraja	1175	2433	2097
3.	Baraka	1435	2611	2249
4.	Baroko	853	1339	1146
5.	Bungin	547	635	543
6.	Buntu Batu	1307	1752	1465
7.	Cendana	377	804	666
8.	Curio	1369	2251	2023
9.	Enrekang	1359	2277	1925
10.	Maiwa	1477	2676	2281
11.	Malua	629	1010	877
12.	Masalle	1477	2157	1846
Total		12855	21488	18506

Source: Enrekang District Social Service, 2021

Based on the table above, it shows quite fluctuating numbers. The data in the table above is the number of additions for each period as BNPT recipients in Enrekang district. Looking at these data, it can be seen that the number of additions is quite significant each period. This shows that the database archiving system is still weak so that there are still many people who have not been registered since the beginning of receiving the assistance.

The amount of Pagan Non-Cash Assistance (BPNT) is Rp. 110,000,-/KPM/month. This assistance cannot be taken in cash and can only be exchanged for rice or eggs at E-Warong. if the assistance is not spent in that month, the value of the assistance will still be stored and accumulated in the Food Aid electronic account.

As stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs no. 25 of 2016 that those who must get the Non-Cash Food Assistance program are called beneficiary families with socio-economic conditions below 25%.

However, this is not the case in Enrekang Regency. In reality, the implementation of the non-cash food assistance program is actually received by people with socio-economic conditions above 25%. Communities receiving non-cash food assistance actually have a capable economic condition.

The author sees that apart from problems that do not only come from the government's inappropriate targeting, in the distribution of non-cash food assistance, other problems also come from the lack of E-warong facilities provided by the government and E-warong parties in supporting the implementation of non-cash programs.

This condition exacerbated the cooperative relationship between the Enrekang Regency government and the E-Warong provider. E-warong parties also sometimes make it difficult for recipients of non-cash assistance programs to obtain E-warong exchange results in the form of rice and eggs because of the limited types of goods provided so that people only take the goods that are available.

Based on these conditions, it is necessary to evaluate the implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program in Enrekang Regency. As revealed by [10] that there are four aspects or indicators that are used to measure policy evaluation, namely aspects or indicators of input, process, output, and benefits. The purpose of this research is to find out and analyze the implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT) program in Enrekang Regency.

II. METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. This approach aims to provide an overview regarding the evaluation of the implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT) program in poverty alleviation in Enrekang Regency. The informants are; (1) Head of BAPPELITBANGDA Enrekang Regency; (2) Secretary of Social Service Enrekang Regency; (3) Cooperation Bank Representatives; (4) Representatives of e-warong owners; (5) BPNT Program Companion Representative in Enrekang Regency; (5) Recipients of the BPNT Program in Enrekang Regency. The data collection techniques carried out are as follows; (1) Interview; (2) Observation; (3) Document Review. The data processing is carried out using qualitative analysis, namely as follows : (1) Data collection stage, (2) Reduction, (3) Data display, (4) Verification, (5) Conclusion.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) is social assistance from the government that is given to underprivileged communities. BPNT is basically social assistance that focuses on distributing basic food support as a staple food for the community. Therefore, electronic cards are distributed to fulfill this need. In this context, BPNT beneficiary communities are referred to as Beneficiary Families (KPM) which have the lowest 25% economic condition according to the implementation area.

The main goal of BPNT is to provide balanced nutrition for the community while increasing economic growth through the development of micro and small businesses using non-cash transactions. Meanwhile, another goal of BPNT is none other than to overcome poverty in Indonesia in order to reduce the burden of spending on food needs for the underprivileged people every month.

Through BPNT, KPM will receive non-cash assistance in the form of an electronic money system that can be spent at certain stalls which he calls the name E-Warong which is a partner of the banking sector as a channeling party in order to obtain food ingredients such as rice, eggs and so on.

As directed by the President of the Republic of Indonesia, Mr. Jokowi Widodo at a closed meeting on the Raskin Program in July 2016, the distribution of Rice for the Poor (Raskin) is replaced by using an electronic card which will be given directly to the target households so that social assistance and subsidies will be distributed in a non-cash manner using the system banking. The new system for distributing food assistance is regulated in Presidential Regulation Number 63 of 2017 concerning Distribution of Non-Cash Social Assistance.

Non-cash social assistance is provided within the framework of poverty alleviation programs which include social protection, social security, social empowerment, social rehabilitation, and basic services. This program is also expected to make it easier for the public to reach formal financial services in banks so as to accelerate financial inclusion programs. Distribution of non-cash social assistance to the community is considered more efficient, right on target, right amount, right time, right quality, and right administration.

The electronic card in question can be used to obtain rice, eggs and other staples at markets, stalls, shops according to the prevailing prices so that the people also obtain a more balanced nutrition. Not only carbohydrates, but also proteins, such as eggs. In addition, the distribution of non-cash social assistance can also accustom people to saving because they can arrange the disbursement of aid funds themselves according to their needs.

A. Preparation Phase

Preparation is the initial stage of activity after the Ministry of Social Affairs determines the ceiling for the Sembako program, district/city areas and implementation mechanisms, as well as distribution banks. This activity includes coordinating implementation, preparing KPM data, opening collective accounts and preparing E-Warong.

Coordination is basically carried out at every level of government. Coordination at the Central Government level is carried out between the Ministry of Social Affairs as the Budget User (PA) for the Sembako program and related Ministries/Institutions (K/L) through the Central Food Social Assistance Coordination Team forum and reported/consulted to the Control Team. Coordination with Ministries/Institutions is carried out to obtain input and directions related to program implementation policies. In addition, coordination is carried out to ensure the legal basis, mechanisms and stages of program implementation, as well as various other administrative procedures. Furthermore, coordination is also carried out at the government level at the provincial and district/city levels.

Coordination is carried out in order; (1) Ensuring the readiness of supporting infrastructure related to the implementation of the Staple Food program; (2) Agree on the process of opening an account and registering/distribution of KKS for KPM; (3) Agree on the implementation of education and outreach; (4) Agree on the distribution time; (5) Mapping risks and challenges that will be faced in implementation and determining potential solutions.

As the results of the interview with Mr. Syamsuddin, S.Pt., M.Sc. as head of BAPPELITBANGDA of Enrekang Regency, that:

"So far, we, BAPPELITBANGDA, have always been building coordination of cross-sectoral roles (Agencies / PDs) within the Enrekang Regency Regional Government. Furthermore, attend and organize BPNT program coordination meetings in order to coordinate directly with related parties/elements. We also encourage the formation of a Coordination Team that involves elements of the Village/Kelurahan, District and other relevant agencies." (Interview on Tuesday, August 9, 2022).

Then added the results of an interview with Mrs. Siti Farisya Mahardika Sari, S.P. as the Secretary of the Enrekang Regency Social Service, revealed that:

"As the responsible agency, we from the Social Service are always preparing plans and strategies that are more optimal in implementing BPNT effectively in Enrekang Regency. In this planning stage, we first prepare by holding coordination meetings with all other relevant agencies. Then prepare the Beneficiary Card (KPM) data. What's more, is preparing to direct the prospective beneficiary community to immediately open an account collectively as well as preparing E-Warong as a place to shop." (Interview on Wednesday, August 24, 2022).

As an initial stage (coordination), the Enrekang District Social Service as the Implementing Service from BPNT always coordinates with the central government lewar Regional BNBA Coordinator and when SP2D is released so that all coordination in the Field can be well coordinated. Furthermore, holding coordination meetings with all stakeholders every month before and after the implementation of the basic food program/BPNT. To further maximize coordination, a Whatsapp group was created for the entire coordination team as a forum for coordination and complaints in the midst of the community.

Then for the next stage, namely by downloading BNBA at Siks – NG and or asking directly to the regional PFM Directorate. This is done through the regional coordinator to be sent Via Email to be forwarded to the Facilitator and Channeling Agent as the basis for the companion and channeling agent to convey it to KPM.

Then in the third step in this preparation stage, then arrange the schedule and place for opening an account. However, first coordinate with the Village government and Social Assistance Officers so that distribution/distribution is carried out in each village (Banks conducting visits).

In connection with the selection of E-warongs/dealing agents, it is carried out based on the distribution and strategic points of KPM spending Aid. However, there will still be a priority scale for them based on the existence of stalls (shops) that have EDS machines as a condition for program distribution. To KPM who have stalls (shops) with strategic places and are worthy of being empowered (KPM Empowerment).

Furthermore, the results of the interview with Mrs. Adel Yudistira Mulya, S.H. as the representative of Bank Rakyat Indonesia, Enrekang Regency, as the BPNT fund distribution partner, said that:

"In terms of preparation, we have started verifying the data that has been received and will verify as BPNT recipients. Furthermore, it is divided into each village/kelurahan and then publishes the account book and activates the ATM. Thus, the data that we have received will be validated immediately so that it is ready for distribution. Until now, we have not encountered serious problems that hinder the running of the BPNT program in Enrekang Regency" (Interview on Monday, 5 September 2022).

Then added by Mrs. Ratnawati, Mrs. Risnawati, and Mr. Suardi as the owners of the E-Warong in Enrekang Regency, revealed that:

"Until now, coordination with the government and the community, including BRI, has been quite good. We always coordinate related to the distribution of groceries to the community. for the preparation stage, we, the owners of the E-Warong, also collaborated with traders, especially suppliers of raw materials from basic necessities to meet the needs of the community." (Interview on Friday, August 26, 2022).

The results of the interviews with the three informants from the elements of the E-Warong owners above show that there is effective coordination, both from government elements, the channeling banks, and community elements as beneficiaries. Through good coordination, it will certainly be able to solve all the problems that arise in the midst of society.

In fact, as a strategic step, the owner of the E-Warong has also collaborated by signing a cooperation agreement with the private sector (entrepreneurs) for staple food raw materials or local vegetable entrepreneurs (from within Enrekang Regency itself) so that they can meet the community's vegetable food needs. Besides being cheap, of course the quality of these vegetables is also better because they are picked directly from the tree.

Then Mr. Jamaluddin and Mr. Syamsir, S.Pd., M.Pd. As a BPNT assistant in Enrekang Regency, said:

"Coordination at the district level is carried out at least once a year, meeting with the district head, regional secretary and Forkopimda elements. But, when it comes to coordination at the sub-district level, almost every distribution we coordinate with the sub-district head, it is the sub-district head who will convey it to the village head and lurah within his area. We, as assistants, conveyed to the sub-district head, the police, and the PKSK that the distribution of basic necessities would be carried out again. (Interview on Saturday, September 10, 2022).

Based on the results of the interview above, it shows that the preparatory stage as the first step in the distribution of BPNT, especially in Enrekang Regency, has been carried out quite effectively. This is marked by quite massive coordination between all related elements so that it makes it easier to implement the BPNT program in Enrekang Regency, especially at this initial stage (preparatory stage).

The end result of communication (work relations) is the achievement of coordination in an effective and efficient way (effective and efficient). Coordination is intended as an effort to unify the activities of organizational work units (units), so that the organization moves as a unified unit to carry out all organizational tasks to achieve its goals. Coordination is a process of mutual agreement that binds various activities or elements (as seen in the process) of government that differ in the dimensions of time, place, component, function and inter-governmental interests that are governed, so that on the one hand all activities on both sides are directed towards government goals. determined together and on the other hand the success of one party is not undermined by the success of the other party.

The data source from the Ministry of Social Affairs/Social Services was born from a proposal by underprivileged residents from the Village/Kelurahan Government. Later the Social Service will deploy a survey team to conduct a survey whether the data is really from underprivileged families or vice versa. Later, after the new survey is carried out, data validation will then be separated which data may enter the category of BPNT or PKH recipients. If it is in the bottom 10% of the order, then it is included in the category of PKH beneficiary candidates. The order of the lowest 20% is included in other Social Assistance recipients. 20% and 30% of the lowest order will be included in KIS assistance recipients, tube subsidies, and so on.

There are villages that are far and remote, making it difficult for them to access the city, so we coordinate with HIMBARA so that they go directly to the field to pick up the ball. So, before the distribution is carried out, we convey it to the District Government and the police regarding the latest data on upgraded BPNT recipients. Furthermore, the village

government will convey this information to its residents, especially BPNT recipients.

Since the beginning, E-Warong has had a decree from the Ministry of Social Affairs. They (E-Warong owners) were directed to make a letter of request for cooperation with Himbara Bank (BRI in Enrekang Regency). Through the application letter, an EDC machine will also be given as a means to make transactions for the purchase of basic necessities by BPNT recipients in accordance with the nominal they receive.

B. Education and Socialization Stage

Education and socialization of the Sembako program is a joint task between the government. Both the central and regional governments as well as the channeling banks and food assistance implementing staff. Implementing education and socialization starting from elements of the government to carry out socialization in stages according to their duties, functions and authorities. Apart from the government, channeling banks also have authority as executors, even the owners/managers of E-Warongs and food assistance staff in the regions.

The objectives of implementing education and socialization of the basic food program as set out in the general guidelines for the 2020 first change of basic food program are; (1) Providing understanding to stakeholders at the central and regional levels regarding the policies and implementation aspects of the Sembako program as a social protection program, particularly regarding the existence of the Sembako program as a development of the BPNT program and the function of the Sembako program as part of the JPS to reduce the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic ; (2) Providing KPM with an understanding of the purpose and mechanism for utilizing the Sembako program assistance funds; (3) Providing understanding to KPM during the Covid-19 pandemic regarding the implementation of health protocols to prevent the spread of Covid-19 during the distribution of KKS and the use of Sembako program assistance funds in e-Warongs; (4) Providing understanding to e-Warong during the Covid-19 pandemic regarding the implementation of health protocols to prevent the spread of Covid-19 in the utilization of Sembako program assistance funds by KPM in e-Warong; (5) Providing information about the complaints mechanism for the Sembako program; (6) Provide understanding to KPM about the importance of fulfilling nutrition in the First 1000 Days of Life (HPK) to prevent stunting through the use of assistance from the Basic Food program; (7) Provide information to KPM regarding the importance of having population documents in the implementation of the National Non-Cash Movement (GNNT).

As the results of the interview with Mr. Syamsuddin, S.Pt., M.Sc. as head of BAPPELITBANGDA Enrekang Regency, said that:

"We also constantly conduct outreach and education at the district, sub-district and village levels. Information dissemination using social (digital) media, placing banners in public places, as well as sub-district and village offices" (Interview on Tuesday, 9 August 2022).

Then added the results of an interview with Mrs. Siti Farisyah Mahardika Sari, S.P. as the Secretary of the Enrekang Regency Social Service, revealed that:

"In this socialization and education stage, of course we do it with various series and objectives to be achieved. First, the implementation of socialization and education itself then determines who is targeted. Furthermore, creating or compiling material that will be presented in the socialization and education activities as well as determining the media tools that will be used in the socialization. In the socialization and education stage, of course it cannot be separated from the activity of examining the stages or process of the socialization and education. (Interview on Wednesday, August 24, 2022).

Socialization and education is carried out every month. This activity is carried out by BPNT assistants in Enrekang Regency and every 3 months it is carried out with the coordinating team for the basic food program and the Social Assistance Task Force (Satgas) for Enrekang Regency.

Until now, socialization is still actively carried out on a regular basis every month and conveyed to all villages/kelurahans to invite them if they wish to carry out further socialization. In terms of preparing the material to be used in socialization and educational activities, of course the organizers also make maximum preparations. Among them are added power points and special material to be delivered and displayed during meetings/socialization so that the material presented is easier for participants to digest.

Furthermore, in making complaint services and other service activities carried out through social utilization so that all activities are shared to become information for all KPM, such as Facebook, Whatsapp, and E-Warong sign banners accompanied by price lists. The flow of education and outreach is to start by holding a coordination meeting between the coordinating team for the basic food program/BPNT to agree on a time and place for socialization each month. Furthermore, at the time and village that has been agreed upon, a written invitation will be sent regarding the implementation of the education and outreach so that all KPM will be present in the education and outreach activities.

Furthermore, the results of the interview with Mrs. Adel Yudistira Mulya, S.H. as the representative of Bank Rakyat Indonesia, Enrekang Regency, as the BPNT fund distribution partner, said that:

"We educate and socialize benefit users related to collective accounts by educating KPM directly that after receiving the account KPM is now registered as a BPNT beneficiary. The media used in the education and socialization activities are via telephone and also direct education to KPM, assistants, distribution agents and local village/kelurahan officials" (Interview on Monday, 5 September 2022).

Then added by Mrs. Ratnawati, Mrs. Risnawati, and Mr. Suardi as the owners of the E-Warong in Enrekang Regency, revealed that:

"From the aspect of providing education and socialization from BPNT organizers, in my opinion it is quite good. Moreover, the companion's telephone number is given directly, so if there is anything we can call directly" (Interview on Friday, 26 August 2022).

The results of the interviews above show that there is a system of providing education and outreach that runs quite effectively. The assistants have carried out their role in providing assistance to the beneficiary communities so that the community does not become deficient in important information related to the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program in Enrekang Regency.

The objectives of implementing education and socialization of the Sembako program are; (1) Relevant Ministries/Institutions; (2) Regional Governments, including the Poverty Reduction Coordinating Team (TKPK) and Provincial, Regency/City and District Food Social Assistance Coordinating Teams; (3) Village apparatus/kelurahan apparatus and ranks below them; (4) Food Social Assistance Implementers; (5) Beneficiary Group (KPM); (6) E-Warong owner/manager; (7) Channeling banks both at the central and branch levels; (8) General public.

Further disclosed by Mr. Jamaluddin and Mr. Syamsir, S.Pd., M.Pd. As a BPNT assistant in Enrekang Regency, said that:

"We conduct outreach through several means. Like in WA groups. In the group it was conveyed that the accompanying party would come to conduct trials on the community for transactions. Through this activity, we also conduct direct education" (Interview on Saturday, 10 September 2022).

We educate the public to remind them to avoid misunderstandings. We also always go around the field so that we can directly meet the person, at least if there are problems, we will directly confirm it.

We always follow the guidelines prepared by the government through the Ministry of Social Affairs. So, it is through this outreach activity that we try to make it understandable to the public.

The media for education and outreach use WhatsApp groups and we sometimes invite the community as well as village officials to a forum. In fact, we always go around the community to follow up to provide further education and outreach to the community because sometimes it's a shame they are shy about asking in forums so I have to visit them one by one randomly to provide education and understanding as well as dig up information regarding complaints- public complaints about the management of this BPNT.

Furthermore, our contact numbers have also been distributed to the public so that they (the public) may contact us at any time. Thus, the community has longer and more extensive time to consult further related to the distribution of BPNT in Enrekang Regency.

So, whenever we have something to convey, we will always coordinate with the sub-district government. Furthermore, the sub-district government will convey directly to the sub-district or village government in its territory. Then the Lurah and Village Head will inform the community so that it is collected through a forum.

Then it was clarified by Mrs. Suhartini, Mrs. Nurhayati, and Mr. Tajrin as the beneficiaries of BPNT Enrekang Regency revealed that:

“Until now, in my opinion, the socialization has been quite good because indeed we are the recipients who always get information saying we want more liquidation, be prepared. However, this is another kodong ji who has never received it, of course you also need information, for example how to enter the recipient's name as well” (Interview on Sunday, September 4, 2022).

Based on the results of the interviews above, it shows that up to now the provision of education and outreach to the Beneficiary Communities has been quite good. However, the government also needs to think further about people who have never registered in the BPNT program to be recommended as beneficiaries as long as they still meet the elements of the requirements.

IV. CONCLUSION

The implementation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BNPT) program has not been effective in overcoming poverty in Enrekang District. This is due to the lack of the role of the local government (Kelurahan/Village) in providing a clear understanding to the community regarding the method of submitting and determining Beneficiary Groups (KPM) so that the community becomes confused and lacks information regarding this matter. The BPNT program has not been fully enjoyed by the poor in Enrekang District. In fact, the presence

of BPNT has not been able to reduce the amount of poverty in Enrekang Regency, and has even increased the number of poor people. At this stage the distribution of BPNT funds in Enrekang Regency has also not been effective. This is indicated by the fulfillment of community requests that have not been fulfilled by the service provider (the owner of the E-Warong) so that the community is forced to take goods that are still available even though these goods are not actually their needs, but due to the minimal availability of goods, they have to take these goods.

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